

HISTORY OF STUDY OF SOMATIC PHRASEOLOGISMS IN GERMAN AND
UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This scientific article analyzes the level of study of somatic phraseology in German and Uzbek languages, and highlights the work of scientists in this field.*

Keywords: *phraseological; language; dictionary; phraseology; translation; antonymy; homonymy; expressiveness features.*

"German-Russian-Uzbek Phraseological Dictionary" is the first example of multilingual comparative and comparative dictionaries in modern Uzbek phraseology. This dictionary contains short word beginnings, conditional abbreviations and vocabulary words written in German and Uzbek languages. Each fixed phrase in the German language given in the educational phraseological dictionary is first interpreted in that language, and then its corresponding alternative translations in the Uzbek and Russian languages are given. The meaning of some ambiguous phraseology is reflected in several variants in all three languages. The purpose of the educational dictionary is to use emotional and expressive language wealth in the development of oral and written speech of pupils and students, the expression of each phraseology in speech is in German after translation into Russian and Uzbek stated in different sentences. The sentences are taken from literary works and forms of oral speech [1].

As a result of our studies, we can note that the number of SFs in this dictionary is significant. According to the "Head of the Word", this dictionary includes more than 700 fixed word combinations with different structures related to all three languages. The results of the study showed that 160 of them (23%) are SFs: *der Arm (3), das Auge (8), der Bart (2), das Bein (6), der Blut (1), die Brust (1), der Daumen (3), die Faust (3), die Ferse (1), der Finger (6), der Fuß (6), das Genick (1), das Gesicht (2), das Haar (5), der Hals (6), die Hand (13), die Haut (1), das Herz (12), die Kehle (1), das Knie (1), der Kopf (21), die Leber (1), der Magen (1), der Mund/ das Maul (16), der Nagel (2), die Nase (12), das Ohr (14), der Rücken (3), der Schoß (3), die Schulter (3), der Zahn (2).*

At this point, it is necessary to recognize the work of Professor Sh.S. Imyaminova, who has been studying the field of phraseology within the German and Uzbek languages for several years. In his textbook "German Phraseology", the scientist analyzed in detail the classification of German phraseological units, the peculiarities of German idioms and the characteristics of phraseological synonyms. At the end of the work, a short German-Uzbek phraseological dictionary, a short German-Uzbek proverb and a short German-Uzbek idiom dictionary increase its value [2].

In the first chapter of the work, phraseologisms about intelligence, ability, and life experience are studied. The author emphasizes the large number of phraseological units involved in this soma due to the fact that "head" is directly related to intelligence, researches SFs by

dividing them into semantic groups such as intelligence, mental acuity, ingenuity, and dwells on translation features [2; 20-b.].

Also, in this study guide, SFs composed of the words *Auge, Haare, Kopf, Lippen, Mund, Nase, Ohr, Stirn, Zähne, Zunge* are analyzed according to their synonymous characteristics [2; p. 48]. Sh. Imyaminova, when translating phraseology and their synonyms, special attention should be paid to the fact that the components of the phraseology are translated from one language to another according to the underlying meaning of the whole phraseology and its synonym, not based on the word-for-word translation of the components of the phraseology. states that [2; 56-b.].

Analyzes of the translation characteristics of SFs were also reflected in the research works of translation scholar Z.Y. Sadikov. The linguist studied the translation of ancient Turkish SFs into German in his doctoral thesis entitled "Comparative analysis of German and English translations of Yusuf Khos Hajib Qutadgu Bilig" [3].

SFs in German and Uzbek languages were studied as a direct object of research in the research work of G.M. Umarjonova entitled "Cross-analysis of phraseologisms with the component "Hand" in the Uzbek languages". In the work, SFs with only the word "Hand"-"qo'l" were analyzed, structural-grammatical and structural-semantic, synonymy, antonymy, homonymy, polysemy, expressiveness features were revealed and classified according to the degree of alternation. Also, according to the results of the research, a dictionary of SFs with "Hand"-"qo'l" component in German and Uzbek languages was developed. [4; 8-b.]. In addition, several articles have been published by young linguists [5;6;7;8;9]

It can be concluded that rich experience has been accumulated in order to research SFs in different aspects in different languages such as Russian, English, German, French, Turkish, Uzbek, Dari. However, language is a set of systems, which should be studied in conjunction with other languages. Although a number of scientific works devoted to the comparative study of phraseologisms of German and Uzbek languages have been created, the fact that somatic phraseology in these two languages has not been thoroughly studied from a linguistic and cultural point of view is a factor that determines the relevance of the research.

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